

PRAGMATIC DISCORDANCE OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK PHRASES IN THE EVENT OF SPEECH ACT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8368922>

Subject. Apart from phraseological units, translation involves some kind of loss of meaning in grammar structures as well. Due to a specific system of every language which differs from each other, translators may struggle with converting text keeping their core meaning. As the grammatical structure of every language have differences that pose problems, translators should analyze that difference and find accurate or proper correspondences in the target language.

Purpose. In order to gain the fullest information about those differences interpreters initially should pay attention to numerous inter-linguistic lexical and grammatical transformations.

Problem. The grammatical structure of language is an important part of its overall system, no less important, in fact, than its lexicon or vocabulary. The elements of the grammatical structure, such as affixes forms of inflection and derivation, syntactic patterns, word order, function words, etc., serve to carry meanings which are usually referred to as "grammatical" or "structural" meanings, as distinct from lexical meanings. The rendering of these meanings in the process of translation is an important problem relating to the general problem of translation equivalence which must be considered at length.

First, there several types of grammatical transformation which are:

- **Substitution**

With this type of transformation translators can substitute a part of speech or form of word by another one. It is obvious that substitution divides into two types which are *substitution of parts of speech* and *the grammatical form of a word*. For example, "he says he will come" – "u kelishini aytyapti" or "he said he would come" – "u kelishini aytdi". In those examples we can see that future simple and future in the past changed into participle and infinitive in target language. The substitution of parts of speech also divides into two types: *obligatory and non-obligatory*. The former type is used when there is not corresponding of part of speech in target language that is used in the source language. "Reach the passage a second time" – "ushbu parchani yana bir bor o'qing". In this translation the article "the" is converted into demonstrative pronoun "ushbu" and "a" changed to number "bir".

- Transposition

This kind of transformation is also understood as a change of words, however, conversion occur with position of linguistic elements in the target language comparing to the source language. There are two types of transposition: *transposition of parts of sentence* and *transposition occasioned by the change of types of syntactic connection in a composite sentence*. “**yesterday, I went to the party which I had been invited**” – “*kecha men taklif qilingan bazmga bordim*”. In this example it is clear that order of words changed in the target language, due to the fact that it is a complex sentence which consists of two independent sentences connected with clause. Another example for compound sentence: “**I bought all necessary things I want**” – “*men o’zim xohlagan barcha narsalarni sotib oldim*”.

- Addition

This type of grammatical transformation assists translators to keep the core meaning of the sentence by adding or changing words where the semantic components of lexical unit are not formally expressed. For example: “**You have no business to say such a thing! – She exclaimed. Why not? Anybody can see it**” – “*Seni bunday so’zlar aytishga haqqing yo’q! – u qichqirdi. Nimaga yo’q ekan? Buni hamma eshitdi*”. In this example, the real translation of the words “*no business, why not, anybody*” has been changed and added extra emotions, such as “*haqqing yo’q, nimaga yo’q ekan, hamma*”, in order to show main idea of the text.

- Omission

It is opposite to addition where some of the words might be omitted in order to keep grammatical redundancy in both languages. “**There are many flowers in his garden**” – “*uning bo’g’ida ko’p gullar bor*”. In this sentence the word “*there are*” has to be translated as “*u yerda bor*”, however, it is necessary to add “*u yerda*”, because the word “*bor*” can give the whole meaning of that. Another example: “**she took her book**” – “*u kitobini oldi*”. Here the word “*her*” omitted, as it is clear that book belongs to her, thus, there is no need to translation of that word.

To conclude with that, translation is a process which every interpreter should care about the core meaning of text while facing some problems related to the equivalences of source and target languages. And finding a good equivalence is one of the important jobs of translators.

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